

Arctic Roadmap for Observing and Data Systems (ROADS)

Practitioner's Handbook

Part I

Deliberative draft for the 2026 Arctic Observing Summit

A product of the Arctic ROADS Advisory Panel.

Text and Diagrams are under deliberation; please contact
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Arctic ROADS Practitioners' Handbook

[Introduction](#)

[Part I: Understanding Arctic ROADS](#)

[1. Background on the Arctic ROADS Process](#)

[1.1 Who is Invested in Arctic ROADS?](#)

[1.2 Who Engages in ROADS and Why?](#)

[Box: SAON's Role in Arctic ROADS](#)

[2. Arctic ROADS Guiding Principles](#)

[1. Inclusion - Bring diverse perspectives into the process;](#)

[2. Equity - Equitably include Indigenous Peoples' and support their participation as equal partners in Arctic ROADS;](#)

[3. Support Societal Benefits - Deliver broadly shared societal benefits from observing and data systems to user groups;](#)

[4. Build on What Exists - Connect and strengthen existing efforts, from local to international projects and networks;](#)

[5. Step-by-Step Progress – Grow through a flexible, evolving structure that allows ideas and priorities to emerge throughout the process.](#)

[3. The Integrated Advisory Process](#)

[3.1 Why Arctic Observing Needs an Integrated Process](#)

[3.2 Who Is Involved and What They Do](#)

[3.3 The Integrated Advisory Process](#)

[4. The importance of Societal Benefits](#)

[4.1 Centering Shared Societal Benefits](#)

[4.2 Identifying Shared Societal Benefits](#)

[4.3 Grounding Information Needs in Societal Benefits](#)

[Box: The US AON Benefit Tool – Linking Observations to Shared Benefits](#)

[5. From Shared Benefits to Shared Arctic Variables](#)

[5.1 The Role of SAVs in the Arctic ROADS Process](#)

[Box: SAVs and Essential Variables: Similarities and Differences](#)

[Box: Wildfire Shared Arctic Variables](#)

[Box: The Arctic Observing Summit and ROADS process](#)

[Transition to Part II](#)

Introduction

The Arctic Roadmap for Observing And Data Systems, or Arctic ROADS, Practitioners' Handbook is a two-part guide for everyone working to make Arctic observing more connected, equitable, and effective. It explains, step-by-step, how to turn shared priorities into coordinated plans for observing and data sharing—linking the needs of people and communities with the institutions, processes, and systems that collect and use Arctic data.

The Handbook brings together lessons from years of dialogue among the growing community of experts now shaping Arctic ROADS. It is both a reference and a companion: something to work from, return to, and adapt as new ideas emerge.

At its heart, Arctic ROADS is a process. It is not a new institution, network, or project. It is a way of organizing collaboration so that observations collected across the Arctic—by Indigenous Peoples, researchers, agencies, and community observers—can be linked to serve widely shared benefits. These benefits are the foundation of Arctic ROADS: they describe how improved observing and data coordination can make lives safer, decisions evidence-based, and the Arctic and the planet more resilient in the face of rapid change.

Expert Panels are the grassroots engines of Arctic ROADS. They form around a theme where better observing and data can provide clear shared benefits. They bring together a diversity of voices—Indigenous experts and Knowledge holders, community leaders, scientists, data managers, agencies, and funders—to turn shared priorities into implementation plans and practical action.

The Practitioners' Handbook is intended to bring the practices of the Arctic ROADS process to life. It describes how to form Expert Panels, identify shared societal benefits, define what needs to be observed, and build practical, ethical plans for implementation. It outlines how the ROADS [Advisory Panel](#) works with Expert Panels through the multi-phase Integrated Advisory Process to guide, connect, and evaluate these efforts.

Every section of this Handbook is written in plain language, with flexibility for groups to adapt the process to their own context. While it provides structure, it does not prescribe a single path. Groups are encouraged to move at their own pace, reflect their own priorities, and evolve as relationships deepen. Key terms and ideas are defined in the [Glossary](#).

The pages that follow outline the full process: *Understanding Arctic ROADS (Part I)* describes the broader ideas. *Part II, Putting ROADS into Practice* walks through each phase of the process, providing examples, resources and examples from prior expert panels. Each phase is supported by the [Process Workbook](#), which contains templates to fill in as you work. Together, they provide a pathway for describing observing systems that not only measure change, but help people navigate uncertainty, protect what they value, and shape a more resilient Arctic future.

Part I: Understanding Arctic ROADS

1. Background on the Arctic ROADS Process

For decades, efforts to observe the Arctic have been wide-ranging but fragmented. Indigenous communities have built deep, place-based knowledge through lived experience and long-term stewardship. Scientists and national agencies have deployed instruments, satellites, and research programs. Together, these efforts have generated an enormous amount of valuable information. Yet too often, this knowledge has been collected, managed, and used in isolation.

The result is a patchwork of observing efforts that does not always meet the needs of people or decision-makers. Observations may be strong in one region, but missing in another. Data may exist for scientific research but be difficult to access or apply in local planning or emergency response. In a region changing as rapidly as the Arctic, these gaps limit our collective ability to understand change, manage risk, and act with confidence.

The consequences are already visible. Subsistence users face increasing uncertainty as wildlife abundance and distribution shift. Communities watch roads, buildings, and pipelines crack as permafrost thaws without observing data to plan and obtain infrastructure funding. Agencies struggle to provide reliable forecasts for shipping safety, wildfire risk, or coastal hazards. Global climate and ocean models still lack critical Arctic data, impeding reliable predictions. These challenges are not isolated failures; they reflect a broader need for better coordination across observing and data systems.

The Arctic ROADS process was created in response to this need. It offers a practical way to connect those who generate, use, and steward Arctic knowledge — from Indigenous Peoples and community observers to scientists, agencies, and decision-makers — around shared priorities. Arctic ROADS does not replace existing networks or projects. Instead, it provides a structured process to align efforts, strengthen connections, and build on what already exists.

At its core, Arctic ROADS is about organizing collaboration around shared societal benefits. It starts by asking what people need from observing systems to live safely, make informed decisions, and sustain Arctic communities and ecosystems. From there, it helps partners work together to identify what should be observed, how data should be shared, and how observing systems can be strengthened over time. In this way, Arctic ROADS supports observing systems that not only measure change, but help people and institutions navigate it.

1.1 Who is Invested in Arctic ROADS?

The creation of Arctic ROADS reflects the interests of many different groups.

- **Indigenous Peoples and communities** want observing systems that respond to their priorities, respect their knowledge systems, create opportunities, and help sustain their ways of life.
- **Scientists** and coordinating bodies (like the International Arctic Science Committee (IASC)) want systematic, high-quality data that support both discovery and applied research.
- **Governments and national agencies** want reliable information to guide investments in infrastructure, emergency response, shipping, and resource management. They also rely on observing data to support policy and regulatory decisions, evaluate foreign and domestic investments, and uphold international commitments on climate, environment, and maritime safety.
- **Regional organizations, including Arctic Council working groups,** want to synthesize and assess Arctic data in order to formulate Arctic-related policy recommendations.
- **Global organizations** want large-scale Arctic data to strengthen climate models, ocean forecasts, and international policy.

By bringing these groups together, Arctic ROADS ensures that observing systems are not shaped by any single interest but reflect a shared understanding of what matters most. ROADS aims to make observing more efficient, strengthening coordination, reducing duplication, and allowing resources to be shared strategically and cost-effectively across networks and sectors.

1.2 Who Engages in ROADS and Why?

Arctic ROADS is an open process driven by self-forming Expert Panels (EPs, see section 3.2) organized around thematic areas, e.g., Harmful Algal Blooms or Wildfires, that would benefit from improved data collection and sharing. Arctic ROADS provides structure, visibility, networking, and planning tools to EPs to support their progress. It is ideal for building observing networks and strategic plans around emerging needs, and can also enhance existing networks and efforts to build new partnerships and data sharing strategies.

ROADS is supported by an Advisory Panel (AP) that interacts with EPs through its Integrated Advisory Process (see section 3 for more), offering further planning perspectives and partnership development. The AP has also guided the development of this Handbook.

Arctic ROADS was developed under the umbrella of the Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks (SAON; see Box 'SAON's Role in Arctic ROADS'). SAON is an international initiative, co-sponsored by the Arctic Council and the International Arctic Science Committee (IASC), with a mission to strengthen and connect Arctic observing. SAON appoints the ROADS Advisory Panel (see section 3.3 for more) and takes responsibility for the results of the ROADS process.

Box: SAON's Role in Arctic ROADS

The Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks (SAON) is the international initiative that oversees Arctic ROADS. SAON created the Arctic ROADS process and appoints the Advisory Panel that guides it. SAON's position gives Arctic ROADS legitimacy and reach: it connects local and national priorities to an international framework, and it ensures that the results of Expert Panels' work through Arctic ROADS are visible to governments, funding agencies, and global organizations.

2. Arctic ROADS Guiding Principles

Guiding Principles have been developed to support those engaged in the Arctic ROADS process throughout their work. They are reflected in the overall arc of the process and embedded in its tools and concepts. The Guiding Principles trace their roots to the leadership of the Arctic Council's (AC) [Permanent Participants](#) (six Indigenous Peoples' organizations with a special relationship to Arctic Nations in the AC) and direction provided by the SAON Board, particularly through the discussions and commitments made at the Second and Third [Arctic Science Ministerials](#). They reflect lessons learned across the Arctic:

1. **Inclusion** - Bring diverse perspectives into the process;
2. **Equity** - Equitably include Indigenous Peoples' and support their participation as equal partners in Arctic ROADS;
3. **Support Societal Benefits** - Deliver broadly shared societal benefits from observing and data systems to user groups;
4. **Build on What Exists** - Connect and strengthen existing efforts, from local to international projects and networks;
5. **Step-by-Step Progress** – Grow through a flexible, evolving structure that allows ideas and priorities to emerge throughout the process.

Together, these principles describe not just what Arctic ROADS does, but how it works, and how people work together within it.

3. The Integrated Advisory Process

The Integrated Advisory Process is how Arctic ROADS turns shared priorities into coordinated action. It provides a structure for collaboration, while remaining flexible enough to reflect different places, knowledge systems, and ways of working. Through ongoing dialogue, learning, and review, Expert Panels and the [Advisory Panel](#) work together to strengthen Arctic observing over time.

3.1 Why Arctic Observing Needs an Integrated Process

Arctic observing is inherently complex. Knowledge is generated by many different actors — Indigenous Peoples, researchers, agencies, networks, and community observers — working across regions, disciplines, and national boundaries. No single organization, discipline or country can define priorities or deliver solutions on its own. Even within a single area, like

permafrost thaw risk, there are often no mechanisms to coordinate between different actors and efforts.

The Integrated Advisory Process exists to help these efforts work together, without losing sight of the people and places that rely on the information. It provides a way to coordinate across this complexity while keeping decision-making grounded in lived experience, shared priorities, and real-world use of information.

By linking EPs and the Advisory Panel in an on-going cycle of dialogue and review, the process supports shared learning, transparency, and accountability. This helps ensure that Arctic observing efforts remain equitable, connected, and focused on delivering broadly shared societal benefits, and not just technical outputs.

3.2 Who Is Involved and What They Do

The Integrated Advisory Process involves two types of panels:

Expert Panels

Grassroots EPs bring together people with relevant expertise, experience, and lived knowledge to co-design observing strategies around thematic topics. Expert Panels put the guiding principles into practice by ensuring Indigenous Peoples are equal partners, benefits are widely shared, existing efforts are built upon, and progress is made step by step.

Expert Panels are the engine of Arctic ROADS. They bring together the people best positioned to define shared priorities, design observing strategies, and move from ideas to action. Expert Panels form around themes, issues, and places where improved observing and data can deliver meaningful societal benefits. They are flexible and self-organizing, while intentionally centering Indigenous leadership and participation in line with the Guiding Principles.

Expert Panels operate within a small set of shared concepts that define their role in Arctic ROADS:

- **Expert Panels are grassroots and expert-driven.**
EPs form around shared needs and are shaped by the people most connected to those needs, rather than being assigned from the top down.
- **Societal Benefits guide the work.**
EPs begin by clearly describing who benefits, how, and why. Observing and data requirements are defined only after benefits are understood.
- **Shared Arctic Variables provide focus.**
When appropriate, EPs identify candidate Shared Arctic Variables or SAVs—key phenomena that require coordinated observing across actors and help connect local priorities to broader Arctic and global benefits.
- **Expert Panels turn priorities into plans.**
EPs are responsible for developing clear, actionable implementation plans that define observing needs, data governance, and pathways to sustainability.

- **Work is connected and accountable.**

EPs work in dialogue with the Advisory Panel, receiving guidance, feedback, and evaluation to help strengthen their outputs and align with broader efforts.

Expert Panels put the Arctic ROADS Guiding Principles into practice. By centering Indigenous leadership and participation, they help ensure that observing priorities can be shaped by Indigenous Knowledges. By focusing on clearly articulated societal benefits, they encourage work that serves many users rather than narrow interests. By building on existing efforts and networks, panels avoid duplication and strengthen coordination. And by working step by step—testing ideas, incorporating feedback, and adjusting scope—they support learning and long-term sustainability.

Together, EPs and the Advisory Panel form a system of distributed stewardship, where responsibility is shared across many actors but coordinated through a common framework.

The Advisory Panel

The Advisory Panel is formally appointed by the SAON Board and includes representatives from national agencies, Indigenous organizations and scholarship, research agencies, scientific networks, and international bodies. Its membership reflects organizations with long-term responsibility for sustaining Arctic observing.

The Advisory Panel supports EPs by helping ensure their work is connected, balanced, and visible beyond individual themes or regions. It applies the Guiding Principles from a cross-cutting perspective and draws on expertise in societal benefits, Indigenous engagement, and coordination across observing systems.

The Advisory Panel has three main roles:

- **Guidance and oversight** – helping EPs stay aligned with Guiding Principles and with one another
- **Connection and integration** – linking EP outputs to existing networks, national strategies, and global efforts
- **Evaluation and accountability** – reviewing work to ensure equitable participation and clearly articulated societal benefits

Together, the Advisory Panel and EPs form a system of shared responsibility, or distributed stewardship. Decision-making is spread across multiple groups, each with its own role, but connected through a common framework. In the Arctic — where observing cannot be managed by a single institution — this polycentric approach is essential.

3.3 The Integrated Advisory Process

The Integrated Advisory Process follows a clear sequence. It begins with a foundational step, moves through four main phases, and ends with evaluation. Part II of the handbook details the phases with further instructions.

Foundational step: Build relationships and shared purpose

Before any technical work begins, time is spent building relationships, trust, and a common understanding of why the work matters. This includes early engagement with the Advisory Panel and participation in Open Partnership meetings, where ideas can be shared, aligned, and supported.

Phase I: Form an Expert Panel

A group is brought together with a clear focus and leadership; this is the Expert Panel (EP). The EP includes people with different types of knowledge and experience, with particular attention to the leadership and participation of Indigenous Peoples.

Phase II: Define and assess societal benefits

Working closely with the communities, rightsholders, and stakeholders most affected, the EP identifies the real-world benefits that better observing could provide. This may involve using established tools (see Box: “The US AON Benefit Tool”) or creating new, community-driven approaches. The goal is to clearly describe how improved observations could support people, decisions, and outcomes that deliver tangible societal benefits.

Phase III: Define observing and data needs

The EP then determines what needs to be observed and what data are required to deliver the benefits identified in Phase II. This includes deciding what should be measured, how often, where, and at what level of detail. The EP also considers how data should be managed, shared, and governed so it can be used effectively and responsibly.

Phase IV: Plan for implementation

The EP develops a practical plan to show how the observing and data needs can be met. This includes identifying partnerships, approaches to data stewardship, and possible funding and sustainability pathways.

Evaluation: Review progress and outcomes

Evaluation is built into every phase of the process and includes a final review at the end. Expert Panels and the Advisory Panel work together to assess whether outputs are practical, equitable, and aligned with Guiding Principles. Independent external review is encouraged to provide additional perspective and credibility.

Through this inclusive and benefit-driven approach, EPs help translate shared priorities—such as safer travel, resilient infrastructure, food security, wildfire readiness, and reliable weather and climate services—into coordinated observing and data strategies that are grounded, equitable, and actionable.

Figure 1: The integrated advisory process weaves together contributions from different expert groups through the four phases of the ROADS Process.

The Integrated Advisory Process is not a one-way process; it is built on ongoing dialogue.

- **Champions:** Each EP has an Advisory Panel “Champion” who follows the work of the EP and provides advice, coordinates communication between the EP and the Advisory Panel, and helps with connections.
- **Open Partnership Meetings:** These gatherings bring EPs, Advisory Panel members, and the broader community together to exchange progress, identify overlaps, and build shared solutions.
- **Feedback Loops:** At each step, EPs receive structured input from the Advisory Panel to strengthen benefits statements, refine requirements, and sharpen implementation strategies.
- The **Advisory Panel learns** from each EP’s experiences, improving the process and guidance over time.

4. The importance of Societal Benefits

The foundation of Arctic ROADS is understanding that observing is not an end in itself. Its purpose is to support gathering and sharing information needed to improve lives, decisions, and resilience across the Arctic and beyond. In short, to deliver societal benefits.

4.1 Centering Shared Societal Benefits

Centering shared societal benefits transforms the way observing is organized and sets the foundation for cooperation within Arctic ROADS. When collaboration begins with shared benefits rather than isolated objectives, partners can more easily recognize common ground and align their efforts. Shared societal benefits establish a common purpose that unites diverse actors, including Indigenous Peoples, local communities, researchers, and agencies, around what truly matters for people and the environment.

The emphasis on shared societal benefits also makes Arctic ROADS more equitable. By grounding coordination in collective needs, the process ensures that the perspectives of Arctic residents, particularly Indigenous Peoples and rightsholders, shape the observing agenda from the start. Benefits are defined with communities, not for them. Centering shared benefits also helps funders and policymakers see where their investments can deliver the most impact and helps communities articulate what outcomes they value most.

4.2 Identifying Shared Societal Benefits

Societal benefits describe the tangible improvements that better scientific data and information sharing can realize across, for instance, safer travel routes, more resilient infrastructure, reliable food and water systems, healthier and more resilient ecosystems, and greater capacity to adapt to a changing climate. Identifying meaningful shared societal benefits allows diverse partners to act independently while moving in concert toward broader societal and environmental outcomes. Systematic assessment reveals how improved information extends benefits across cultures, regions, and knowledge systems, leading to the identification of observing solutions that link local priorities to national and regional needs, and global understanding.

Arctic ROADS offers a starting point for identifying shared societal benefits – the International Arctic Observing Assessment Framework (IAOAF, see Box: “The International Arctic Observations Assessment Framework”) – but encourages its participants to develop an individualized approach that fits their needs.

4.3 Grounding Information Needs in Societal Benefits

Expert Panels begin by connecting their broad theme or focus area to collectively identified societal benefits, such as safety, resilience, environmental stewardship, or preparedness. These benefits help clarify *why* better observing matters and provide a lens for understanding how information supports people, decisions, and outcomes. Existing benefit frameworks can be a helpful starting point.

They then explore how information is actually used by discussing real-world situations, known as *use cases*. A use case—such as designing a new bridge in an area prone to permafrost thaw—describes who needs information, what decisions they face, what knowledge they currently rely on (including Indigenous and community knowledge), and what information is

missing. Looking at both current and desired conditions helps reveal where observing and data systems support these decisions well, and where they fall short.

By examining patterns across multiple use cases, panels can identify the key observable phenomena that sit at the heart of shared societal benefits. Areas for improvement may point to needs for new observations, better coordination of existing systems, improved data sharing, or stronger support for community-led monitoring. In Arctic ROADS, these shared priorities are organized via Shared Arctic Variables (SAVs), which provide a bridge between societal needs and coordinated observing strategies, which are explored in the next section.

Box: The US AON Benefit Tool – Linking Observations to Shared Benefits

Website: <https://usaon.org/apps/benefit-tool>

The US AON Benefit Tool helps users visualize how observations and data connect to real societal benefits. It links what is measured (satellites, *in situ* sensors, community monitoring) to the data products and decisions they support, such as search-and-rescue readiness, infrastructure planning, or ecosystem management.

Each evaluation maps ‘inputs → data → applications → benefits’, highlighting where observing systems are strong and where critical gaps remain. The tool allows experts and community users to rate these links and describe them in their own words, producing a clear picture of how observing efforts deliver public value.

As more people use the tool, its library of assessments reveals patterns across the Arctic—showing where coordination or investment could have the greatest impact. Within the Arctic ROADS process, the Benefit Tool supports Phase II by offering a structured yet flexible way to express benefits in both quantitative and qualitative terms, consistent across Expert Panels.

Figure 2: This example BENEFIT assessment diagram from the [2025 Arctic Report Card](#) illustrates the value chain linking AON observations and data via indicators to Arctic Societal Benefit Areas. BENEFIT performance and criticality scores are provided by subject matter experts.

5. From Shared Benefits to Shared Arctic Variables

A Shared Arctic Variable is something measurable – like sea ice thickness – backed by a set of documentation that describes how it should be observed to meet specific societal needs. They are defined by expert panels by linking requirements for observing and data/information systems to the ways that people use information in the real world.

[SAVs](#) provide a way to organize and act. They are the coordinating anchor of the ROADS process, describing phenomena that process participants agree are both critical to observe and too complex for any single group to address alone.

5.1 The Role of SAVs in the Arctic ROADS Process

SAVs are a central tool within the wider Arctic ROADS process, helping link these efforts to larger coordination goals across disciplines, regions, and observing systems.

By centering the process on SAVs, Arctic ROADS ensures that observing systems are designed around widely shared benefits and strategic efficiency. SAVs help:

- Identify information needs for communities, governments, regions, and global science.
- Focus investments and resources where coordination can deliver impact.
- Link local observations to national, regional, and international needs.
- Provide clear priorities that funders, policymakers, and practitioners can target for action.

In this way, SAVs are both the journey and the destination. The journey is the process of defining them - through dialogue, benefit assessment, and the application of the Guiding Principles. The destination is a set of agreed upon variables that guide how observing systems are built, connected, and sustained.

Once defined, SAVs provide a structure for:

- **Designing cost-effective observing systems** that meet real needs.

- **Specifying requirements** for what data must be collected, how often, and with what tools.
- **Creating strategies** for implementation that are supported by many actors.
- **Building accountability**, because progress can be measured against whether SAVs are being observed.

Figure 3. Shared Arctic Variables becoming the center discussion point between many perspectives, in both the what would be the observable, why is it important, and how it should be measured, stored, archived, and used.

5.2 Understanding SAVs in the ROADS process

Shared Arctic Variables are not limited to traditional scientific or operational measurements. They may emerge from Indigenous Knowledges, community priorities, or practical needs, and they are considered “shared” because they cut across disciplines, cultures, and regions. By

providing a common focus and shared language, SAVs enable coordination among diverse efforts while respecting different ways of knowing.

Building on the shared benefits identified through use cases, SAVs offer a structured framework for coordinated observing, similar to the role played by Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) and Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) in global observing systems (see Box X). Examples of emerging Arctic SAVs—including those developed by Expert Panels focused on permafrost, wildfires, sea ice, and salmon—are described later in this document.

Box: SAVs and Essential Variables: Similarities and Differences

SAVs are not the first attempt to coordinate observing through “variables”. The Global Climate Observing System defines **Essential Climate Variables (ECVs)**. The Global Ocean Observing System uses **Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs)**. Other frameworks also exist.

SAVs share much with these earlier efforts. They provide a common focus, encourage standardization, and help channel investment into coordinated areas. Like ECVs and EOVs, they create an agreed vocabulary for planning and assessment.

But SAVs are also different in important ways:

- **Shared across knowledge systems:** Unlike ECVs and EOVs, SAVs can include not just scientific measures, but also include Indigenous Knowledges and community-defined priorities.
- **Broadly defined benefits:** SAVs are chosen because they deliver benefits at multiple levels — local, regional, national, and global. ECVs and EOVs are often defined in terms of scientific or policy needs alone.
- **Arctic-specific design:** SAVs reflect the unique conditions of the Arctic, community-driven priorities, and the expertise of people who live and work in the Arctic.

In short, SAVs build on the strengths of earlier frameworks but go further by integrating diverse voices and grounding the process in the specific challenges and needs inherent to the Arctic context. They can also develop in coordination with global Essential Variables, which capture the operational and scientific dimensions at broader scales. In doing so, SAVs embody the Arctic ROADS Guiding Principle of coordinate and integrate, ensuring that Arctic observations strengthen – and are strengthened by – global observing systems.

Box: Wildfire Shared Arctic Variables

The Wildfire expert panel based in Finland identified “Ignition identification” as the key Shared Arctic Variable from their discussions. The common information need identified by the group was to quickly identify/attribute fire ignition. This helps responders recognize what is burning, why it is burning and how a fire spread, which leads to a more effective response from rescue services. Better information on fire ignition also contributes to fire science and improved future management.

Box: The Arctic Observing Summit and ROADS process

The Arctic Observing Summit (AOS) has provided the main stage for shaping Arctic ROADS for over a decade. Repeated discussions at the AOS made it clear that a systematic, co-produced process was needed for Arctic observing coordination. The Arctic ROADS process is the outcome of this dedicated and thoughtful dialogue across many disciplines and groups.

AOS has also been instrumental in shaping and embedding the concept of shared societal benefit at the core of Arctic ROADS. Discussions made clear that sustainable observing cannot depend only on scientific objectives; it must show direct value to people and communities. This recognition gave rise to the systematic approach that Arctic ROADS now follows: start with benefits, assess them collectively, and then determine what needs to be observed to achieve them.

The AOS continues to play a critical role today. It is where Expert Panels share their progress, where new ideas for SAVs are tested, and where feedback from the wider community strengthens the process. In this way, the AOS remains the backbone of dialogue that ensures observing activities are relevant, inclusive, and effective.

Transition to Part II

Expert Panels are essential to Arctic ROADS. They are where shared priorities take shape, where diverse knowledge systems come together, and where observing strategies move from concept to action. Part I of this Handbook was created to provide all those investing in Arctic ROADS with a common foundation of understanding.

Part II builds on this foundation, walking through the Integrated Advisory Process step-by-step and providing tools and examples to support EPs as they move through each Phase.